

CYCLIC COMPRESSIVE STRESS-STRAIN MODEL FOR FRP- CONFINED ENGINEERED CEMENTITIOUS COMPOSITES (ECC)

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the development of stress-strain model for fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) - confined engineered cementitious composites (ECC) under cyclic compression. Test database for FRP-confined ECC was firstly collected, followed by the evaluation of the existing cyclic models developed for FRP-confined normal concrete. New equations were also developed based on the test results of FRP-confined ECC. Different components in the cyclic model, including envelope curve, unloading curves, reloading curves, plastic strains and stress deterioration, were discussed in detail. Finally, cyclic model was proposed for FRP-confined ECC, and good agreements between predictions and test results were obtained.

KEYWORDS

Engineered cementitious composites (ECC); Confinement; Cyclic compressive behavior; Stress-strain model

INTRODUCTION

Engineered cementitious composites (ECC) is regarded as a type of high-performance fibre-reinforced cementitious material (Li, 2003; Xu et al., 2022). Due to the fibres in the mixture, ECC can achieve distinctive enhanced tensile ductility compared with normal concrete. Due to the fibre-bridging effect through the microcracks, the width of tensile cracks in ECC can be controlled and prevented from continuing growing, which leads to the multiple cracking behaviour (Zhu et al., 2022). In recent years, ECC has been widely used in various engineering applications to improve the performance of different structural members, such as avoiding large tensile cracks and protecting steel rebars in the tensile zone in reinforced concrete beams (Yang et al., 2018), providing additional lateral confinement to the core concrete in hybrid columns (Al-Gemeel and Zhuge, 2019) as well as strengthening the plastic hinge zone of beam-column joints (Dong et al., 2021).

Though the tensile performance of ECC is prominent, its compressive behaviour is similar to normal concrete and will endure the brittle failure as well when reaching the peak strength. Adopting fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) lateral confinement is an effective approach to improve the compressive performance of ECC. Dang et al. (2020), Li et al. (2022), Yuan et al. (2021 and 2022) and Jiang et al. (2023) have conducted experimntal investigations on FRP-confined ECC stub columns to observe the axial compression performance. With the obtained test results, design models that can predict the ultimate conditions as well as analytical models that can predict the compressive stress-strain curves have also been developed accordingly for FRP-confined ECC under monotonic compression. Apart from the monotonic loading, ECC could also be subjected to various more complicated loading conditions, like cyclic and seismic loadings. Therefore, understanding the cyclic compressive performance of FRP-confined ECC is of vital importance especially due to the fact that ECC and FRP are usually used together for seismic retrofitting (Zhou et al., 2023). Dang et al. (2020) and Li et al. (2022) investigated the behaviour of FRP-confined ECC stub columns under cyclic compression. It was noted that the envelope curve of cyclically loaded FRP-confined ECC was close to the stress-strain curve of the counterpart - monotonically loaded FRP-confined ECC, which has the same behaviour as FRP-confined normal concrete. It was also observed that the deformability could be further enhanced for FRP-confined ECC specimens under cyclic compression. There has been extensive research on the

cyclic modelling for FRP-confined normal concrete, which can describe the unloading/reloading paths, plastic deformation and stress degradation behaviour (Bai et al., 2021 and Zhou et al., 2021). To the best of the authors' knowledge, there is no cyclic stress-strain model developed for FRP-confined ECC in the literature. Meanwhile, the applicability of existing cyclic models developed for FRP-confined normal concrete to FRP-confined ECC remains to be unknown.

Therefore, this study focuses on the cyclic modelling for FRP-confined ECC. Test database was firstly collected as the basic for the model development. Typical cyclic models that were developed for FRP-confined normal concrete were then evaluated, with detailed discussions on the individual component in the cyclic model, including envelope curve, unloading curves, reloading curves, plastic strains and stress deterioration. New equations were also developed based on the test results of FRP-confined ECC. Finally, cyclic model was proposed to predict the cyclic stress-strain behaviour of FRP-confined ECC. The predictions generated by the proposed model were compared with the corresponding test results.

TEST DATABASE FOR FRP-CONFINED ECC

This section of the paper summarises the existing research on FRP-confined ECC. A test database was collected from five different sources as shown in Table 1. It consists of 86 specimens in total, in which 74 specimens were tested under monotonic compression and 12 specimens were tested under cyclic compression. All the specimens had the height to diameter ratio of 2, which is typically adopted for the investigation of FRP-confined concrete under pure axial compression. The confining materials vary from glass FRP (GFRP), carbon FRP (CFRP), polyethylene terephthalate FRP (PET FRP) to polyethylene naphthalate (PEN FRP). Both experimental investigations and modelling including design-oriented and analysis-oriented have been carried out for FRP-confined ECC, and most of the studies were focused on the monotonic compressive behaviour. Only Dang et al. (2020) and Li et al. (2022) conducted the cyclic compressive tests with 12 FRP-confined ECC specimens. Meanwhile, the modelling on FRP-confined ECC under cyclic compression is absent at the current stage. Therefore, this study focuses on the development of cyclic stress-strain model for FRP-confined ECC, which will contribute to the understanding of the behaviour of FRP-confined ECC under more comprehensive loading conditions.

Table 1: Test database for FRP-confined ECC

Source	Specimen number	Loading type	Size (mm)	f'_{c0} (MPa)	ϵ_{c0} (%)	FRP type	$\frac{f'_{cu}}{f'_{c0}}$	$\frac{\epsilon_{cu}}{\epsilon_{c0}}$	E_f (GPa)	ϵ_{frp} (%)	$\frac{f_{lu,a}}{f'_{c0}}$
Dang et al. (2020)	12	Monotonic & Cyclic	$D=100$ $H=200$	64.6-66.0	0.35	GFRP CFRP	1.28 – 3.92	4.20 – 23.69	91.1, 236.9	2.19, 1.79	0.14 – 1.17
Li et al. (2022)	18	Monotonic & Cyclic	$D=100, 200$ $H=200, 400$	40.0	0.41	GFRP CFRP	1.42 – 4.96	6.49 – 34.59	39.2, 255.0	1.60, 1.79	0.27 – 1.34
Yuan et al. (2021)	15	Monotonic	$D=150$ $H=300$	28.2	0.44	PEN FRP PET FRP GFRP	1.12 – 3.34	6.52 – 39.41	27, 17.9, 100.5	5.8, 8.3, 2.4	0.16 – 0.83
Yuan et al. (2022)	32	Monotonic	$D=100-500$ $H=200-1000$	51.6	0.27	PET FRP GFRP	1.03 – 1.62	3.37 – 4.19	17.9, 100.5	8.3, 2.4	0.10 – 0.22
Jiang et al. (2023)	9	Monotonic	$D=100$ $H=200$	35.2, 40.0	0.26	PET FRP	1.01 – 1.71	2.81 – 11.40	15.99	9.85	N.A.

Notes: D and H are the nominal diameter and height of the specimens; f'_{c0} and ϵ_{c0} are the unconfined compressive strength and the corresponding strain of ECC; f'_{cu} and ϵ_{cu} are the ultimate compressive strength and ultimate axial strain at FRP rupture. ϵ_{frp} is the FRP rupture strain obtained from material tests. $f_{lu,a}$ is the actual confinement pressure at FRP rupture with the expression of $f_{lu,a} = 2E_f t_f \epsilon_{h,rupt} / D$, in which E_f and t_f are the elastic modulus and thickness of confining FRP and $\epsilon_{h,rupt}$ is the actual hoop strain at FRP rupture.

CYCLIC STRESS-STRAIN MODEL

Typical cyclic stress-strain curve for FRP-confined concrete encompasses the envelope curve, unloading curves and reloading curves, in which the unloading curves and reloading curves are also related to the plastic strain and stress deterioration. In this section of the paper, the different components are discussed and developed in detail for cyclically loaded FRP-confined ECC.

Envelope curve

Envelope curve is the upper boundary of cyclic stress-strain curve and is close to the stress-strain curve under monotonic compression for FRP-confined concrete. Therefore, the envelope curve for cyclically loaded FRP-confined ECC can be generated with the stress-strain model for monotonically loaded FRP-confined ECC. Lam and Teng's design-oriented model (Lam and Teng, 2003) was developed for FRP-confined normal concrete and was widely adopted to predict the monotonic compressive behaviour of FRP-confined concrete. Therefore, it is adopted herein to predict the envelope curve for FRP-confined ECC under cyclic compression. In Li et al. (2023), it was found that existing equations for the ultimate conditions developed for FRP-confined normal concrete could not perform well for the predictions for FRP-confined ECC. New equations were proposed to predict the ultimate compressive strength f'_{cu} and ultimate axial strain ε_{cu} according to the collected test data of FRP-confined ECC, with the expressions for f'_{cu} and ε_{cu} shown as follows:

$$\frac{f'_{cu}}{f'_{co}} = 1 + 2.9(\rho_K - 0.01)(\rho_\varepsilon)^{0.9} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\frac{\varepsilon_{cu}}{\varepsilon_{co}} = 1 + 21\rho_K^{0.98}\rho_\varepsilon^{1.02} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

in which f'_{co} and ε_{co} are the compressive strength and the corresponding compressive strain of unconfined ECC; ρ_K and ρ_ε are the confinement stiffness ratio and strain ratio with the following expressions:

$$\rho_K = \frac{K_l}{(f'_{co}/\varepsilon_{co})} = \frac{2E_f t_f}{(f'_{co}/\varepsilon_{co})D} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\rho_\varepsilon = \frac{\varepsilon_{h,rupt}}{\varepsilon_{co}} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

in which D is the diameter of confined ECC; K_l is confining stiffness; E_f and t_f are the elastic modulus and thickness of confining FRP; $\varepsilon_{h,rupt}$ is the FRP hoop rupture strain. Consequently, Eqs. 1-4 are used for the prediction of ultimate conditions in Lam and Teng's model (Lam and Teng, 2003). Typical comparisons between the predicted results and test results for the monotonic stress-strain curve of FRP-confined ECC are shown in Figure 1. The close agreements indicate that the modified Lam and Teng's model (Lam and Teng, 2003; Li et al., 2023) is also applicable to predict the envelope curve for FRP-confined ECC under cyclic compression.

Figure 1: Comparisons of monotonic stress-strain curves between test results and predicted results for FRP-confined ECC (Li et al., 2023)

Unloading curves

FRP-confined ECC presents a similar unloading behaviour to that of FRP-confined normal concrete, which is a nearly linear portion at the initial stage, followed by an obviously nonlinear portion at the end stage. Typical existing unloading models (Lam and Teng, 2009; Yu et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2012; Hany et al., 2015; Li et al., 2018), which were developed for FRP-confined normal concrete, were adopted to evaluate their performance on the prediction of unloading paths for FRP-confined ECC. Figure 2 shows the typical comparisons. In general, Wang et al.'s model (Wang et al., 2012) can generate the closest unloading curves compared with test curves, which indicates that it is applicable to

the prediction of unloading behaviour of FRP-confined ECC. It should be noted that for the evaluation of the five existing unloading models as presented in Figure 2, actual unloading strain ϵ_{un} , unloading stress σ_{un} and plastic strain ϵ_{pl} were used to ensure that the prediction accuracy was dependent on the unloading model only.

Figure 2: Evaluation of different unloading models

Plastic strains

Plastic strain is a key parameter controlling the shape of the unloading path. It equals to the axial strain at the intersection point between the unloading curve and the zero-horizontal axis. Test results of plastic strain, together with the corresponding unloading strains, were extracted from the test cyclic stress-strain curves for FRP-confined ECC as presented in Figure 3a). Based on the test data, a new equation is proposed through regression analysis to describe the relationship between plastic strain and unloading strain for FRP-confined ECC with the following expression:

$$\epsilon_{pl} = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 < \epsilon_{un} \leq 0.002 \\ 1.255(\epsilon_{un})^{1.2}, & 0.002 < \epsilon_{un} \leq \epsilon_{cu} \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

Figure 3b) presents the comparisons between test results and predicted results. The close agreement shows the good performance of the proposed equation as shown in Eq. 5.

Figure 3: Plastic strains for FRP-confined ECC

Stress deterioration

Stress deterioration φ is a parameter used to depict the damage and degradation behaviour of FRP-confined concrete under cyclic loadings, which is expressed with the ratio between the new stress in the reloading curve and the old stress in the unloading curve at the same unloading strain. In the current study, the values of stress deterioration φ at different unloading strains were calculated based on the available test data of cyclically loaded FRP-confined ECC and are plotted in Figure 4. In the current database, all the reloading strains are larger than 0.002. In this range, the stress deterioration can be considered independent of the unloading strain as shown in Figure 4, which is a similar behaviour to FRP-confined normal concrete. The average value of $\varphi = 0.936$ was obtained by regression analysis using the test data for the range of unloading strain $0.002 < \varepsilon_{un} \leq \varepsilon_{cu}$. Similar to the existing stress deterioration model developed for FRP-confined normal concrete (Lam and Teng, 2009; Yu et al., 2015), φ is assigned to be 1.0 for $0 < \varepsilon_{un} \leq 0.001$ and linear relationship between the two points of (0.001, 1) and (0.002, 0.936) is adopted in the range of $0.001 < \varepsilon_{un} \leq 0.002$ for φ and ε_{un} . Therefore, the equation of stress deterioration is expressed in Eq. 6 and also adopted in the prediction model of cyclic stress-strain curve for FRP-confined ECC.

$$\varphi = \begin{cases} 1, & 0 < \varepsilon_{un} \leq 0.001 \\ 1 - 64(\varepsilon_{un} - 0.001), & 0.001 < \varepsilon_{un} \leq 0.002 \\ 0.936, & 0.002 < \varepsilon_{un} \leq \varepsilon_{cu} \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

Figure 4: Stress deterioration for FRP-confined ECC

Reloading curves

The typical reloading path of FRP-confined ECC is featured with a first linear portion starting from the plastic strain point $(\varepsilon_{pl}, 0)$ followed by a second nonlinear portion intersecting with the envelope curve. Smooth transition is ensured between the two portions. Lam and Teng 's model (Lam and Teng, 2009), which was developed for FRP-confined normal concrete, adopts the linear curve from the plastic strain point $(\varepsilon_{pl}, 0)$ to the reference point $(\varepsilon_{ref}, \sigma_{new})$ and a parabolic curve afterwards until the reloading curve intersects with the envelope curve. It covers the features of the reloading behaviour of cyclically loaded FRP-confined ECC. Therefore, Lam and Teng's reloading model (Lam and Teng, 2009) is used to capture the reloading paths for FRP-confined ECC in the current study.

PROPOSED CYCLIC STRESS-STRAIN MODEL AND VALIDATION

Different components in the cyclic stress-strain model for FRP-confined ECC, including envelope curve, unloading and reloading paths, plastic strains as well as stress deterioration, have been discussed in detail in the previous section of this paper. Lam and Teng's model (Lam and Teng, 2003) was modified with the new equations of ultimate compressive strength and ultimate axial strain (Li et al., 2023). It could provide close predictions of the stress-strain curve for FRP-confined ECC under monotonic compression, which is also regarded as the envelope curve of FRP-confined ECC under cyclic compression. Five typical unloading models were evaluated and Wang et al.'s unloading model

(Wang et al., 2012) was found to generate the closest predictions for FRP-confined ECC. Based on the available test data, new equations for predicting the plastic strain (Eq. 5) and stress deterioration (Eq. 6) were proposed for FRP-confined ECC. Meanwhile, Lam and Teng's reloading model (Lam and Teng, 2009) was selected to capture the characteristics of the reloading behaviour of FRP-confined ECC. With these determined components, cyclic stress-strain model of FRP-confined ECC can be developed. Figure 5 shows the typical comparisons between the predicted curves and test curves. The close agreements demonstrate the good performance of the proposed cyclic model for FRP-confined ECC.

Figure 5: Comparisons of cyclic stress-strain curves between test results and predicted results

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents the modelling of cyclic stress-strain behaviour of FRP-confined ECC. A database on FRP-confined ECC was collected. Different components in the cyclic stress-strain model were discussed in detail. The applicability of existing models that were developed for FRP-confined normal concrete was evaluated for FRP-confined ECC and new equations were also developed accordingly based on the test results of FRP-confined ECC. The proposed cyclic model, which consists of the modified Lam and Teng's envelope model (Lam and Teng, 2003; Li et al., 2023) and Wang et al.'s unloading model (Wang et al., 2012) together with the newly proposed plastic strain model and stress deterioration model (Eqs. 5 and 6) as well as Lam and Teng's reloading model (Lam and Teng, 2009), can provide close predictions on the cyclic stress-strain behaviour of FRP-confined ECC compared with test results.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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